

ONE YEAR OF BY JHOVE! EXPLAIN YOURSELF

JHOVE is one of the most widely used tools in digital preservation, but anyone who uses it will be familiar with the challenges that accompany its use. Causes of these problems vary, ranging from a lack of understanding of the impact of validation errors, to outdated training materials, and a graphical user interface (GUI) considered not user-friendly. By JHOVE! Explain Yourself is a special interest group hosted by the Open Preservation Foundation (OPF) that brings together members of the OPF as well as interested parties within the digital preservation community who are interested in evolving JHOVE and discussing their issues with peers.

JHOVE THE THREE PILLARS

JHOVE DOCUMENTATION

The JHOVE documentation was outdated and challenging for new users. This pillar focuses on revising existing content and developing new guidance materials. The team began by converting the documentation from Java to Markdown to improve integration and collaboration. Since then, internal guides and live GitHub tutorials tailored to JHOVE have been created.

Documentation updated:

- An Introduction to JHOVE
- Getting Started with JHOVE
- PDF-HUL module
- JPEG-HUL module

ERRORS & WARNINGS

Users found JHOVE's error & warning messages, especially for complex formats like PDF, overwhelming and unclear. This pillar addresses specific issues. The team have worked on analysis, walk-throughs, and updated the JHOVE GitHub Wiki with their findings.

Errors & Warnings updated:

- TIFF-HUL-3 Unknown data type
- TIFF-HUL-6: Tag Count mismatch
- TIFF-HUL-8: Tag type mismatch
- TIFF-HUL-26: StripOffsets not defined
- TIFF-HUL-27: StripByteCounts not defined
- TIFF-HUL-28: StripOffsets inconsistent with StripByteCounts
- TIFF-HUL-60: More than 50 IFDs in chain, probably an infinite loop
- PDF-HUL-45: Malformed filter
- PDF-HUL-85: No document catalogue dictionary

FIRST YEAR RESULTS

28 INSTITUTIONS
ON THE MAILINGLIST

46 PEOPLE
ON THE MAILING LIST

4 PRESENTATIONS
ONE EACH QUARTER

Entries on the task spreadsheet

86 TASKS
IN THE SPREADSHEET

18 ATTENDEES
ON AVERAGE TO EACH MEETING

12 MONTHLY
VIRUTAL MEETINGS

USER FRIENDLINESS

Using JHOVE requires patience and support; the web application, desktop application, and the command line are all different, which often leads to incohesive results. Recognising this, members of the group have since developed a new GUI prototype, which we hope to implement in the coming year.

NEW GUI PROTOTYPE

WHAT'S NEXT

ALTERNATE
TIMEZONES

BETTER
GUIDANCE

VISUALISE
PROGRESS

DEVELOP A
NEW GUI

DEVELOP A
ROADMAP

JOIN THE
GROUP